

The Coupling Constants Series – a Star's Stability and Collapse – 8T

O Manor

August 16, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the main equations of the new framework of variational manifolds, it is possible to explain the process of star's stability and collapse. In particular, it is possible to explain it from two different angles. First by opposing symmetries breaking, curvature converging inward is equal to the curvature diverging outward to reach stability. We can also choose a more obvious root by comparing short- range forces such as gravity, to the long ranged forces, in due time gravity will overcome those forces, by using the arrow of time.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. It is possible to reason the stability of the star in two ways, which are identical almost. The first is more general, that is by the opposing symmetry breaking of mass generation and force generation. Those two eliminate each other perfectly to achieve stability. By the primorial, we have proven the curvature diverging to be associated with the term $8 + 1$ and the Quark masses series with the symmetry breaking of the inverse kind, $8 - 1$ given by the series of total masses of each fermion generation:

$$19,600 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 56 \rightarrow 0.113 \dots$$

$$19,600 * 9 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow \frac{56}{9} =$$

$$176,400 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 6.3$$

That is to say that the curvature diverging inward is equal to the curvature diverging outward, and so the matter formation described by the term (1.48) is stable. If so, so does the star, as it is a cluster of fermions. We can choose a more direct root to describe the stability of a star. That Is by comparing gravity to the forces extending or radiating from the star outward. The key point is that with time, gravity of the star can get stronger.

As we currently regard gravity as a composite element, as time goes by, the primorial is generating larger and larger net variations, which could change the ratio of the gravitational "constant" of a star given by equations (2.2) and (2.3):

$$[(2N_{gravity}) + (3)] + N_{V1} + N_{V2} + N_{V3} = \left[2N_{gravity} + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad (2.2)$$

$$[2N_{gravity} + 2] \rightarrow [2N_{gravity}] \quad (2.3)$$

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3}$$

$$[N_{VK1}, N_{VK2}, N_{VK3}] \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$K1 \dots KN \in \mathbb{R}$$

However, the net variation N_{VK3} suddenly vanish from the combination and being replaced by a distinct net curvature element that is larger and in agreement with the arrow of time. now the gravitational constant of the star is stronger while the forces extending outward are the same.

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4}$$

$$N_{VK3} \neq N_{VK4}$$

The structure of the gravity is invariant to the change of the element. Since the total spin is invariant, i.e. two, there is not a change in the nature of gravity; the structure is the same while the composite element could be different.

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK3} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

$$[(2N_0) + (3)] + N_{VK1} + N_{VK2} + N_{VK4} \rightarrow 2N_0 + 2$$

While the forces expending which are not a composite are the same, at a certain stage those gravitational interactions will supersede the forces extending outward, which will mean that the curvature converging will exceed the curvature diverging, and so this will ignite the collapse. That analysis is more detailed than the first root, given by the inverse symmetries and a lot more complicated as gravity is a composite interaction that seems to be only partially understood even with the recent advancement of the coupling series and the main equation (1). The key point to take from that analysis is that gravity due to being a composite and time variant can get larger over time, while the independent interactions, given by the primorial, which is a scalar function that do not include the time parameter, are the same in magnitude. That creates a long-term advantage toward the gravitational effect over the independent interactions. The result of such a framework is such that with large time increments, the probability for a collapse of a star is ever increasing. That agrees to what we have previously stated about gravity. That Gravitons are infinite in kind, and are short ranged due to spin two trait, which vanishes.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

Manor Ohad